

Research Article

Projecting Multiple Stochastic Integral unto the Wiener Functional Space Using Iterated Integrals

Ojo- Orobosa V.O

Department of Mathematics and Statistics, Delta State Polytechnic, Ozoro.
Delta State, Nigeria. Email address: orobosavera@gmail.com

Abstract

Any square- integrable functional of the Wiener process has a canonical representation in terms of the integrals. The key of these representation is to define multiple stochastic integral of the form $\int_{G^n} \varphi(g_1, g_2, \dots, g_n) W(dg) \dots W(dg_n)$ where φ is (in general) a random integrand δ -adapted in a suitable sense. In this paper, we construct projections with respect to stochastic integral unto the Wiener functional space and establish formulae for the transformation of multiple stochastic integrals under two operations; (a) projection formula for the projection of a multiple stochastic integrals onto $L^2(\Omega, F_W, \mathcal{A})$ and (b) an iterated formula.

Keywords: *square- integrable, canonical representation, iterated integrals, wiener functional, random integrand, transformation, projection formulae and multiple stochastic integrals.*

Received: 14/06/18

Accepted: 11/09/18

Introduction

In mathematics, Wiener space is the collection of all continuous function on a given domain (usually a sub interval of the real line), taking value in metric space (usually n-dimensional space in Euclidean space). Wiener space is useful in the study of stochastic process whose sample path are continuous function. It is named after the American

This work is licensed under a [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 Unported License](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/)
ISSN: 1597 - 9928 Science and Education Development Inst., Nigeria

mathematician Norbert Wiener. It could be define as; consider $E \subseteq \mathfrak{R}^n$ and a metric space (M, d) , the classical Wiener space $C_0(E; M)$ is the space of all continuous function $f: E \rightarrow M$ ie for every fixed t in E

$$d(f(s), f(t)) \rightarrow 0 \text{ as } |s - t| \rightarrow 0$$

In almost all applications, one takes $E = [0, T]$ or $[0, \infty)$ and $M = \mathfrak{R}^n$ for some n in N . The Wiener process is used to represent the integral of a white noise Gaussian process and so it is useful as a model of noise in electronics engineering. The Wiener process denoted by W_t is characterized by the following properties

$W_0 = 0$ almost surely

W has independent increment; for every $t > 0$ the future increment $W_{t+\mu} - W_t, \mu \geq 0$ are independent of the past values, $W_s, s < t$.

W has Gaussian increment: $W_{t+\mu} - W_t$ is normally distributed with mean and variance $\mu, W_{t+\mu} - W_t \sim \mathcal{N}(0, \mu)$

W has continuous path with probability 1, W_t is continuous int.

The independent increment means that if $0 \leq s_1 < t_1 \leq s_2 < t_2$ then $W_{t_1} - W_{s_1}$ and $W_{s_1} - W_{s_2}$ are independent random variables, and the similar condition holds for n increments (Stock and Varadhan, 1979).

Multiple Wiener Integral

Let us examine the multiple wiener integrals by recalling the following multiplication formula of the multiple wiener integral which is embedded in the following lemma

Lemma 2.1

Let $f \in L^2([0, 1]^p), g \in L^2([0, 1]^q)$ then we have

$$I_p(f)I_q(g) = \sum_{n=0}^{p \wedge q} \frac{p! q!}{n!(p-n)!(q-n)!} I_{p+q-2n}(f \otimes_n g)$$

$$= I_p(f)I_q(g) = \sum_{n=0}^{p \wedge q} \frac{p! q!}{n!(p-n)!(q-n)!} I_{p+q-2n}(f \widehat{\otimes}_n g) \quad (2.1) \text{ where } f \otimes_n g \text{ is}$$

the contraction of order n of the tensor $f \otimes g$ i.e the partial scalar product of f and g in $L^2([0, 1]^n)$ and $f \widehat{\otimes}_n g$ is its symmetrization. This is stated without prove

Multiple Stochastic Integral

Let us define a collection of subset of a fixed rectangle $\mathcal{G}$ in $\mathfrak{R}^n$ to be $\mathcal{M}$. Given set $H_1, H_2, \dots, H_n \in \mathfrak{R}(\mathcal{G})$ let define their support relative to $\mathcal{M}$ as the set of $\mathcal{M}$ $J_{H_1}, J_{H_2}, \dots, J_{H_n} = \cap \{B: B \in \mathcal{M}\}$ and $B \cap H_i \neq \emptyset$ for $[1 \leq i \leq n)$ with the convention that if no such set B then the support is taken to be all of $\mathcal{G}$. The intersection of all the set in $\mathcal{M}$ is the support of the empty collection of sets (*i.e* $n = 0$) and its denoted by J . Let also assumed that the support of any collection of set $H_1, H_2, \dots, H_n$ is contained in $\mathcal{M}$. This assumption can only be true by only enlarging a given collection of set $\mathcal{M}$. If $g_1, g_2, \dots, g_n$ are points in $\mathcal{G}$, their support will be written as $J_{g_1}, J_{g_2}, \dots, J_{g_n}$. It therefore means that $g_1, g_2, \dots, g_n$ are $\mathcal{M}$ - independent if no point is contained (Wikipedia) in the support of the remaining ones.

For $\mathcal{M} = \{\text{all closed set in } \mathcal{G}\}$, $J_{g_1}, J_{g_2}, \dots, J_{g_n}$ is just $\{g_1, \dots, g_n\}$ so that $\mathcal{M}$ - independent means distinct. Also for $\mathcal{M} = \{\text{all convex sets in } \mathcal{G}\}$, the support of n point is their convex hull and the points are $\mathcal{M}$ - independent if and only if they are extreme points of their convex hull.

When $\mathcal{G} \subset \mathfrak{R}_+^n$ and $\mathcal{M} = \{Y_g: g \in \mathcal{G}\}$ where Y_g is the closed rectangle bounded by the origin and g

Then $J_{g_1}, J_{g_2}, \dots, J_{g_n}$ is the smallest set in $\mathcal{M}$ which contains $g_1, g_2, \dots, g_n$
For further illustration, when $\subset \mathfrak{R}_+^n$, and $\mathcal{M}$ is obtained by $\{X_g: g \in \mathcal{G}\}$ where $X_g = \{j \in \mathcal{G}: j_i \leq g_i \text{ for some } i\}$. Then for $g_1, g_2, \dots, g_n \in \mathcal{G}$, $J_{g_1, g_2, \dots, g_n} = \cup v_{g_i}$. Moreover $\mathcal{M} = \{\cup_{i=1}^n Y_{g_i}: n < +\infty \text{ and } g_1, g_2, \dots, g_n \in \mathcal{G}\}$.

In this example, n points are unordered if and only if they are pair wise unordered.
Suppose $\hat{\mathcal{G}}^n$ is the subset of $\mathcal{M}$ - independent points in $\mathcal{G}^n$ then for a given collection $\mathcal{M}$, $\hat{\mathcal{G}}^n$ would be mean less for sufficiently large n . For instance if $\mathcal{M} = \{Y_g\}$ is the collection of rectangles bounded by the origin and $g \in \mathcal{G} \subset \mathfrak{R}_+^n$, then $\hat{\mathcal{G}}^n$ is empty for $n > m$. That is no more than m points can be $\mathcal{M}$ - independent. For extreme cases, $\mathcal{M} = \{\mathcal{G}\}$, $\hat{\mathcal{G}}^n$ is empty for all $n \geq 1$

Let define ε -support relative to $\mathcal{M}$ of $H_1, H_2, \dots, H_n \in \mathfrak{R}^n(\mathcal{G})$ by

$J_{H_1, H_2, \dots, H_n} = J_{B(\varepsilon, H_1), B(\varepsilon, H_2), \dots, B(\varepsilon, H_n)}$ if given a subset H of $\mathcal{G}$ defining $B(\varepsilon, H)$ as the set of points in $\mathcal{G}$ of Euclidean distance at most ε from H for $\varepsilon > 0$ and let $J_{H_1, H_2, \dots, H_n}^{(\cdot)}$ denote the union over all $\varepsilon > 0$ of ε -support of $H_1, H_2, \dots, H_n$

Remark 2.1

The ε - support of $H_1, H_2, \dots, H_n$ increases to $J_{H_1, H_2, \dots, H_n}^{(\cdot)}$ as ε decreases to zero and $J_{H_1, H_2, \dots, H_n}^{(\cdot)}$ is contained in the support of $H_1, H_2, \dots, H_n$ (Wikipedia)

Let $(\Omega, \mathcal{F}, \mathcal{P})$ be a fixed probability space and let $\{\mathcal{F}(H): H \in \mathfrak{R}(\mathcal{G})\}$ be a family of sub- δ -algebra of $\mathcal{F}$ which is increasing in the sense that $H \subset B$ implies that $\mathcal{F}(H) \subset \mathcal{F}(B)$ and let $(W(H): H \in \mathfrak{R}(\mathcal{G}))$ be a wiener process such that $\mathcal{F}_W(H) \subset \mathcal{F}(H)$ and $\mathcal{F}_W(H)$ is independent of $\mathcal{F}(H)$ for all H in $\mathfrak{R}(\mathcal{G})$ then these conditions are true.

For every collection of rectangles $H_1, H_2, \dots, H_n$ such that $\prod_{i=1}^n H_i \subset \hat{\mathcal{G}}^n$
 $\mu(H_i \cap J_{H_1, H_2, \dots, H_n}) = 0;$

For each $n \geq 1$, the mapping $g = (g_1, g_2, \dots, g_n) \dots \dots J$ is a continuous map from $\mathcal{G}^n$ to the collection of compact sets under the Hausdorff metric:

$$p(H : B) = \left(\max_{x \in H} \min_{y \in B} |x - y| + \max_{x \in B} \min_{y \in H} |x - y| \right)$$

For every collection of rectangles $H_1, H_2, \dots, H_n$ in $\mathcal{G}$

$\forall \varepsilon > 0 \quad \mathcal{F}(J_{H_1, H_2, \dots, H_n}) = \mathcal{F}(J_{H_1, H_2, \dots, H_n})$ since $\mathcal{F}_W(H) \subset \mathcal{F}(H)$ for all H in $\mathfrak{R}(\mathcal{G})$, condition (iii) implies the following which we shall refer to as (iv)

For every collection of rectangles $H_1, H_2, \dots, H_n$ in $\mathcal{G}$

$$\mu(J_{H_1, H_2, \dots, H_n} - J_{H_1, H_2, \dots, H_n}^{(\cdot)}) = 0 \quad (2.1)$$

If $\mathcal{F}_W(H) = \mathcal{F}(H)$ for all H , then condition (iii) and (iv) are equivalent, condition (ii) and (iii) is a continuity condition.

For a $\mathcal{M}$ satisfying condition (i) to (iii), we shall now define multiple stochastic integral of order n

$$\phi = W^n = \int_{\mathcal{G}^n} \phi, W(dg_n)$$

For integrands $\phi(\omega, g), (\omega, g) \in \Omega \times \mathcal{G}^n$ satisfying

(a1) ϕ is $\mathcal{F} \times \mu^n$ measurable.

(a2) for each $g \in \hat{\mathcal{G}}^n$, ϕ is $\mathcal{F}(J_g)$ - measurable

(a3) $\int_{\mathcal{G}^n} E \phi_g^2 dg < \infty$

The space function satisfying (a1-a3) is denoted by $L_\mu^2(\Omega \times \hat{\mathcal{G}}^n)$ for ϕ and θ in $L_\mu^2(\Omega \times \hat{\mathcal{G}}^n)$ define

$\langle \phi, \theta \rangle = E \int_{\mathcal{G}^n} \phi_g \theta_g dg$ and let ϕ denote the summarization of ϕ , i.e $\phi =$

$\frac{1}{n!} \sum_{\alpha} \phi_{n(g)}!, x(g) = \text{permutation}$. Call ϕ atomic if $\phi(\omega, g) = \alpha(\omega) I_H(g)$ where I_H is the indicator function of a product of rectangles $H = \prod_{i=1}^n H_i$ such that $H \subset \hat{\mathcal{G}}^n$.

Multiple Wiener Integrals (MWI)

We shall define the multiple Wiener integrals (MWI's) of the following two types

$$I_n(f) = \int \dots \int f(g_1, \dots, g_n) dW_{g_1}, \dots, dW_{g_n} = \int f(g) dW_g^n$$

$$J_n(f) = \int \dots \int f(g_1, \dots, g_n) W_{g_1}, \dots, W_{g_n} dg_1, \dots, dg_n = \int f(g) X_g^n dg$$

Where $n = 1, 2, \dots$ while dealing with integral I_n resp. J_n , we will assume that (I) resp. (J)

(I): $W_g = 0$ a.s for some $g_0 \in \mathcal{G}$

(J) : W is mean square continuous

For W a Wiener process, f is taken to be a function in $L_2(\mathcal{G}^n, dg^n)$ and $(n!)^{-\frac{1}{2}}$ is an isomorphism on $\hat{L}_2(\mathcal{G}^n, dg^n)$ (the Hilbert space of all symmetric functions in $L_2(\mathcal{G}^n, dg^n)$) into $L_2(W)$. However in accordance to the Wiener process, it is necessary and more reasonable to expect that functions $f(g_1, \dots, g_n)$ of the form $\phi_1(g_1) \dots \phi_n(g_n), \phi \in \mathcal{F}(J_g)$ are admissible integrands and their integral is $I_n(f)$ is the iterated integral. $|\phi_1) \dots |(\phi_n)$ when $\phi_1, \dots, \phi_n$ are orthogonal. This imply that $\mathcal{F}(\otimes^n \mathcal{G})$ is the proper class of integrands for the MWI's I_n : and similarly $\pi_2(\otimes^n \mathcal{G})$ is the proper (Chang *et al.*, 2009) class of integrands for the MWI J_n .

Iterated Integrals

In this section, we shall discuss the iterated integral as the result of applications of integrals to a function of more than one variable. For instance, $f(x, y)$ or $f(x, y, z)$ in a way that each of the integrals consider some of the variables as given constants i.e the function $f(x, y)$, if y is considered as a given parameter can be integrated with respect to x , $\int f(x, y)dx$. The result is a function of y and therefore its integral can be considered if this is done, the result become the iterated integral. The order in which the integrals are computed is important in iterated integrals, particularly when the integrand is not continuous on the domain of integration (Hung and Cambanis, 1978). For the purpose of this paper, we shall discuss some result that will help our understanding on iterated integrals.

Iterated, Adapted and Future Increments Independent Integrals

We shall maintain in this section that W is a Wiener process as stated in section 2.2 and start by exploring the relationship between the MWI's and the stochastic integrals by establishing that each MWI can be transformed and written as an iterated integral. That is for $f_n \in L_2(\widehat{\otimes}^n \mathcal{G})$

$$\int f_n(g) dW_{g_n}^n = \int_{\mathcal{G}} \left(\int \left(\dots \left(\int_{\mathcal{G}} f_n(g_1, \dots, g_n) dW_{g_1} \right) \dots \dots dW_{g_{n-1}} \right) dW_{g_n} \right) \quad (3.1) \quad \text{where the}$$

iterated integral remains as defined.

Let H_0 be a Hilbert space and $\mathcal{M}_{I;H_0}^n$ be the set of all H_0 - valued step functions $f(g)$ on $\mathcal{G}^n$ then

$\mathcal{M}_{I;H_0}^n$ is an inner product space with inner product $\langle f, h_0 \rangle = \int \int \langle f(g), h(s) \rangle d^{2n} \mathcal{G}(g, s)$ and its completion is denoted by $L_{2;H_0}(\widehat{\otimes}^n \mathcal{G})$. It is obvious that $L_{2;H_0}(\widehat{\otimes}^n \mathcal{G}) \cong L_2(\widehat{\otimes}^n \mathcal{G}) \otimes H_0$ under the correspondence $(\phi_1 \otimes, \dots \otimes \phi_n) \xi \leftrightarrow (\phi_1 \otimes, \dots \otimes \phi_n) \otimes \xi$. [9]

Thus each element in $L_{2;H_0}(\widehat{\otimes}^n \mathcal{G})$ has an orthogonal development of the form

$$\sum e_{\tau_1, \dots, \tau_n}^\alpha (\phi_{\tau_1} \otimes, \dots \otimes \phi_{\tau_n}) \xi_\alpha$$

where $\{\phi_\tau, \tau \in \Gamma\}$ and $\{\xi_\alpha, \alpha \in H\}$ are continuous in $L_2(\mathcal{G})$ and H_0 respectively.

Consider the following chain of maps

$$\begin{aligned}
 L_2(\otimes \hat{\mathcal{G}}) &\rightarrow_{\pi_1} L_{2;\delta_1}(\otimes^{n-1} \mathcal{G}) \rightarrow_{\pi_2} \dots \rightarrow_{\pi_{n-1}} L_{2;\delta_{n-1}}(\mathcal{G}) \rightarrow_{\pi_n} \delta_n \quad \text{defined first by} \\
 &\phi_{\tau_1} \otimes \dots \otimes \phi_{\tau_n} \rightarrow_{\pi_1} \left(\int \phi_{\tau_1} dW \right) \phi_{\tau_3} \otimes \dots \otimes \phi_{\tau_n} \\
 &\rightarrow_{\pi_2} 2^{\frac{1}{2}} \Phi \left(\int \phi_{\tau_1} dW \widehat{\otimes} \int \phi_{\tau_2} dW \right) \phi_{\tau_3} \otimes \dots \otimes \phi_{\tau_n} \rightarrow \dots \\
 &\rightarrow_{\pi_{n-1}} \{(n-1)!\}^{\frac{1}{2}} \Phi \left(\int \phi_{\tau_1} dW \widehat{\otimes} \dots \widehat{\otimes} \int \phi_{\tau_{n-1}} dW \right) \phi_{\tau_n} \\
 &\rightarrow_{\pi_n} (n!)^{\frac{1}{2}} \Phi \left(\int \phi_{\tau_1} dW \widehat{\otimes} \dots \widehat{\otimes} \int \phi_{\tau_n} dW \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

then by the same argument used for defining θ_n , each π_q can be extended to a bounded linear onto (not one to one) map with norm $q^{\frac{1}{2}}$. It is paramount to know that π_n is the stochastic integral, and that on δ_{q-1} valued step function π_q behave like the stochastic integral when the "extra" variables are fixed. The iterated integral in (4.1) is now defined to be $\pi_n \circ \dots \circ \pi_1(f_n)$ and the equation follows

Let $\mathcal{G} = [a, b]$ and $I_n(f_n) = I_n(\hat{f}_n)$

then we obtain from (3.1)

$$\begin{aligned}
 \int_a^b f_n(g) dW_g^n &= n! \int_a^b \left(\int_a^{g_1} h \dots \left(\int_a^{g_2} \hat{f}_n(g_1, \dots, g_{n-1}, g_n) \right) dW_{g_1} \dots dW_{g_{n-1}} \right) dW_g \\
 &= \int_a^b h_n(g_n) dW_{g_n} \quad \text{where } h \text{ is} \\
 &\text{adapted to } W. \text{ This will be made clearer (in the prove of theorem 3.1).}
 \end{aligned}$$

Let consider the following definition that would be very useful and necessary as we proceed.

Def: A step function $f = \sum_u^M f_m I_{(a_m, b_m]}$ in $L_{2;\delta_2(W)}(\mathcal{G})$ is called adapted if each f_m is $B(W_g, a \leq g \leq a_m)$ – measurable. The closed subspace of $L_{2;\delta_2(W)}(\mathcal{G})$ generated by the adapted simple function is denoted by $L_{2;\delta_2(W)}^{ad}(\mathcal{G}) = L_{2;\delta(W)}^{ad}(\mathcal{G}) \cap L_{2;\delta_2(W)}^*(\mathcal{G})$

Lemma 3.1

If $f \in L_2(\otimes^n \mathcal{G})$ is a step function then $h(g_n) = \int_0^{g_2} h(\dots (\int_0^{g_2} f(g_1, \dots, g_{n-1}, g_n) dW_{g_1}) \dots) dW_{g_{n-1}}$

Is an adapted step function and (3.2)

$$\int_a^b \int_a^g h \dots \int_a^{g_1} f(g) dW_g^n = \int_a^b \left(\int_a^g h \dots \left(\int_a^{g_2} f(g_1, \dots, g_{n-1}, g_n) dW_{g_1} \right) \dots dW_{g_{n-1}} \right) dW_{g_n} \quad (3.2)$$

where both integrals are defined in the usual way as the corresponding integral over the entire interval of $f(g_1, \dots, g_n) I_{(g_1 < \dots < g_n)}$

Theorem 3.1

$g \left(L_2^{ad} \delta_2(W)(\mathcal{G}) \right) = \delta_2^0(W)$ and thus each δ_2 functional θ of W admits the stochastic integral representation

$$\theta - \mathcal{M}(\theta) = \int f(g) dW_g \quad \text{where (the non-necessarily unique) } f \text{ is adapted } \left(f \in L_2^{ad*} \delta_2(W)(\mathcal{G}) \right).$$

Proof

It suffices to prove the second assertion of the theorem first that $\theta \in \hat{\mathcal{G}}_n$, so that $\theta = I_n(\hat{f}_n)$ for some $\hat{f}_n \in L_2(\otimes \hat{\mathcal{G}})$. If ϕ is a step function in $L_2(\otimes \hat{\mathcal{G}})$, it becomes glaring that

$$\hat{\phi} = \sum_{\pi \in \Pi} \hat{\phi} I_{(g_{\pi_1} < \dots < g_{\pi_n})}$$

$$I_n(\hat{\phi}) = n! I_n(\hat{\phi} I_{(g_1 < \dots < g_n)})$$

where $\pi = (\pi_1, \dots, \pi_n)$ is the permutation of $(1, \dots, n)$ and Π is the set of all such permutation. Now let $(\hat{\phi}_n)$ be a sequence of step function in $L_2(\otimes \hat{\mathcal{G}})$ with $\hat{\phi}_n \rightarrow \hat{f}_n$,

Then

$$\hat{\phi}_n I_{(g_1 < \dots < g_n)} - \hat{\phi}_m I_{(g_1 < \dots < g_n)} = \frac{1}{n!} \|\hat{\phi}_n - \hat{\phi}_m\|$$

Implies that $\{\hat{\phi}_n I_{(g_1 < \dots < g_n)}\}$ is Cauchy and its limit can be denoted by $\hat{f}_n I_{(g_1 < \dots < g_n)}$

Then

$I_n(\hat{f}_n) = \lim_m I_n(\hat{\phi}_m) = \lim_n n! I_n(\hat{\phi}_m I_{(g_1 < \dots < g_n)})$, then h_n is clearly a step function in $L_2, \hat{\mathcal{G}}_{n-1}(\mathcal{G})$ adapted to W by lemma 4.1 and by the continuity of π_q 's

$h_m \rightarrow \pi_{n-1} o, \dots o \pi_1 (n! \hat{f}_n I_{(g_1 < \dots < g_n)}) = h_n$. It follows that $h_n \in L_2, \hat{\mathcal{G}}_{n-1}(\mathcal{G})$ is adapted to W and satisfies

$$I_n(\hat{f}_n) = \lim_m \pi_n(h_m) = \pi_n(h_n) = \mathcal{F}(h_n)$$

For a general $\theta \in \delta_2(W)$, we have

$$\theta - \mathcal{M}(\theta) = \sum_{n \geq 1} I_n(f_n) = \sum_{n \geq 1} \mathcal{F}(h_n) = \mathcal{F}\left(\sum_{n \geq 1} h_n\right)$$

Where $h = \sum_{n \geq 1} h_n$ belongs to $L_{2, \delta_2}^*(\mathcal{G})$ since $\sum_{n \geq 1} \|\mathcal{F}(h_n)\|^2 = \sum_{n \geq 1} (\|I_n(f_n)\|^2 < \infty)$ and also adapted to W since each h_n is from (Chang *et al.*, 2009) the definition of $\hat{f}_n(g_1, \dots, g_n)I_{(g_1 < \dots < g_n)}$ in the proof of theorem 4.1 and lemma 4.1. it is clear that equation (4.2) is valid for all $f_n \in L_2(\otimes \hat{\mathcal{G}})$ where both integrals in (4.2) are defined as the corresponding integrals of $\hat{f}_n(g_1, \dots, g_n)I_{(g_1 < \dots < g_n)}$ (Chang *et al.*, 2009)].

Considering the stochastic integral of future increments independent function, let $f = \sum_{m=1}^M f_m I_{(a_m, b_m]}$ in $L_{2, \delta_2}(W)(\mathcal{G})$ be the future increment independent if each f_m is independent of the increment of W after a_m . The closed subspace of $L_{2, \delta_2}(W)(\mathcal{G})$ which is generated by the future increment independent step function is given by $L_{2, \delta_2}^{fii}(W)(\mathcal{G})$ and its elements are called future increment independent (*fii*) functions.

Projection Formulae

In this section we shall be discussing the projection formulae, which actually is the main focus of this research. There are formulae for projecting a stochastic integral unto the space of wiener functional and also for representing multiple stochastic integrals as iterated integral. This we shall present in the following sub topics.

Integrands moment densities and projection formulae

The multiple stochastic integral is isometry in nature, this property can be interpreted as;

Suppose for each $n \geq 1$, and $g \in \mathcal{G}^n$ then $\{\phi_{n,m}(g): m \geq 1\}$ is said to be a complete orthogonal basis for the space of square integrable $\mathcal{F}(J_g)$ -measurable random variable, let assume that $\phi_{n,m}(g)$ is a symmetric function in g , then the multiple stochastic integral isometry property is the set of "incremental" random variables.

$$[\phi_{n,m}(g)W(dg_1)W(dg_2) \dots W(dg_n); n \geq 0, m \geq 1, g \in \mathcal{G}^n] \quad (4.1)$$

Is an orthogonal collection of random variable which are also orthogonal to the $\mathcal{F}(J)$ -measurable random variable (Wikipedia).

Note that the increments dg_1 in (4.1) are “outward” from (J_g) , this is reflected in the next proposition stating that the symmetrized integrands are uniquely determined as moment densities.

Also the collection of variables in (4.1) in conjunction with the $\mathcal{F}(J)$ -measurable variable are complete in $L_2(\Omega\mathcal{F}_W(\mathcal{G}), p)$ if $\mathcal{F}(H) = \mathcal{F}_W(H)$ for all H in $\mathfrak{R}(\mathcal{G})$. (Wikipedia).

Proposition 4.1

Let $\tau \in c$. Then for each $g \in \hat{\mathcal{G}}^m$,

$$E\left[W(dg_1)W(dg_2), \dots, W(dg_m)\tau^0 W^n[\mathcal{F}(J_g)]\right] dg_1 dg_2, \dots, dg_m = n^! \hat{\tau}(g) \delta_{nm} \quad (4.2)$$

Such that the linear functional $f \rightarrow E \int_{\hat{\mathcal{G}}^n} f(g) W(dg_1) W(dg_2), \dots, W(dg_m) \tau^0 W^n$

Defines a symmetric finite signed measure on the δ –algebra of subset $\Omega \times \mathcal{G}^m$ generated by $\mathcal{M}$ -adapted atomic functions, the measure is absolutely continuous with respect to $\rho x \mu^2$ measure, and the Radon-Nikodym derivatives is $n^! \tau \delta_{n,m}$

In view of the definition of Randon-Nikodym deravatives (Kallenberg, 1991) proposition 4.1 is simply a restatement of the isometry property of the multiple stochastic integral.

In the following preposition $L_\alpha^2(\Omega x \hat{\mathcal{G}}^n, \mathcal{F}_W(\cdot))$ is defined in the same way as $L_\alpha^2(\Omega X \hat{\mathcal{G}}^n)$ Except with δ –algebra $\mathcal{F}(H)$ replaced by $\mathcal{F}_W(H)$ for all $H \in \mathfrak{R}(\mathcal{G})$ (Chang *et al.*, 2009).

Proposition 4.2 (projection formula).

For each $\tau \in L_\alpha^2(\Omega X \hat{\mathcal{G}}^n)$ there is $\hat{\tau} \in L_\alpha^2(\Omega X \hat{\mathcal{G}}^n, \mathcal{F}_W(\cdot))$ such that

$$\hat{\tau}(g) = E[\hat{\tau}(g) I_{\mathcal{F}_W}(J_g)] \text{ for } g \in \hat{\mathcal{G}}^n \quad (4.3)$$

and for such $\hat{\tau}$ and all $H \in \mathcal{M}$

$$E[\tau^0 W^n I_{\mathcal{F}_W}(H)] = (\hat{\tau}_n^0 W^n)(H) \quad (4.4)$$

Proof:

By the completeness of multiple stochastic integrals in $L^2(\Omega, \mathcal{F}_W(\mathcal{G}), \mathfrak{b})$

(see proposition 4.3 below) and the fact that $E[\tau^0 W^n I_{\mathcal{F}_W}(J)] = 0$ there exist a collection

$\{\phi_m : m \geq 1\}$ with $\phi_m \in L_\alpha^2(\Omega X \hat{\mathcal{G}}^n, \mathcal{F}_W(\cdot))$ such that

This work is licensed under a [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 Unported License](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/)
ISSN: 1597 – 9928 Science and Education Development Inst., Nigeria

$$E[\tau^{\circ} W^n | \mathcal{F}_W(\mathcal{G})] = \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \phi_m^{\circ} W^m$$

Now by proposition 5.1 with $\mathcal{F}$ replaced by $\mathcal{F}_W$

$$E \left[W(dg_1)W(dg_2), \dots, W(dg_m) E[\tau^{\circ} W^n | \mathcal{F}_W(\mathcal{G}) | \mathcal{F}_W(J_g)] \right] / dg_1, dg_2, \dots, dg_m = m! \phi_m(g)$$

So that

$$E \left[W(dg_1)W(dg_2), \dots, W(dg_m) \tau^{\circ} W^n | \mathcal{F}_W(J_g) \right] / dg_1, dg_2, \dots, dg_m = m! \phi_m(g) \quad (4.5)$$

on $\hat{\mathcal{G}}^m$. Comparison of equation (5.2) and (5.5) reveals that $\phi_m(g) = E \left[\hat{\tau}(g) \delta_{n,m} | \mathcal{F}_W(J_g) \right]$ a.s $g \in \hat{\mathcal{G}}^m$.

Thus

$\phi_m(g) = 0$ for a.s $g \in \hat{\mathcal{G}}^m$ unless $m = n$. So if $\hat{\tau}$ is defined by $\hat{\tau} = \phi_n$ then $\hat{\tau}$ satisfies equation (4.3) and (5.4) is true for $H = \mathcal{G}$. Since each of (5.4) is a martingale relative to $\{\mathcal{F}_W(H): H \in \mathcal{M}\}$, (5.4) is true for all $H \in \mathcal{M}$. Finally since $\hat{\tau}$ is uniquely determined on $\hat{\mathcal{G}}^n$ up to a set of $\mathbb{b} \times \mu^n$ measure zero by Eq. (4.3).

Similarly $\hat{\tau} \in L^2_{\alpha}(\Omega X \hat{\mathcal{G}}^n, \mathcal{F}_W(\cdot))$ satisfying (4.3) and also (4.4) (Chang *et al.*, 2009).

Theorem 4.1 (Iterated integration formula):

Suppose that $\mathcal{M}$ and $\hat{\mathcal{M}}$ each satisfy condition (i)-(iii) see (section 3.2), and that $\hat{\mathcal{M}} \subset \mathcal{M}$. Then for $\theta \in L^2_{\alpha}(\Omega X \hat{\mathcal{G}}^m)$ the class $\mathcal{M}$ stochastic integral $\theta^{\circ} W^n$ can be represented as a sum of class- $\hat{\mathcal{M}}$ integrals

$$\theta^{\circ} W^n = E \left[\theta^{\circ} W^n | \mathcal{F}(j) \right] + \sum_{m=1}^n \binom{n}{m} \phi_m^{\circ} W^m \quad (4.6)$$

Where the integral $\phi_m \in L^2_{\alpha}(\Omega X \hat{\mathcal{G}}^m)$ satisfy

$$\phi_m(g) = \left(\hat{\theta}(gx(\cdot)) I_{j_g^{n-m}} \right)^g \circ W^{n-m} \text{ for a.e } g \in \hat{\mathcal{G}}^m \quad (4.7)$$

For each fixed g , the integral on the right side of Eq.(4.7) is define relative to the collection of set $\mathcal{M}_g$.

Completeness of multiple stochastic integrals and an exponential formula):

Here we shall apply the iterated integration formula to one of the classes of sets $\mathcal{M}$ consisting of all closed subset of $\mathcal{G}$ and $\mathcal{F}(H) = \mathcal{F}_W(H)$ for all $H \in \mathcal{R}(\mathcal{G})$. Let the multiple Wiener integrals be the associated integrals and let $\hat{\mathcal{G}}^n$ be the set of n distinct point in $\mathcal{G}$ and for θ in $L^2(\hat{\mathcal{G}}^n)$, let $\theta \circ W^n$ be a multiple Wiener integral of order n .

Proposition 5.3 (completeness of multiple stochastic integrals):

Let $\mathcal{M}$ be a collection of sets such that $\mathcal{M}$ and $\{\mathcal{F}_W(H)\}$ satisfy condition (i)-(iii). Then every square -integrable $\mathcal{F}_W(\mathcal{G})$ -measurable random variable Z has a representation of the form $Z = E[Z | \mathcal{F}(J)] + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} Z_n \circ W^n$

(5.8)

Where $Z_n \circ W^n$ are stochastic integrals defined relatively to $\mathcal{M}$ and $J = \cap \{B: B \in \mathcal{M}\}$.

Proof :

The proposition is very familiar (Wikipedia; Hajek and Wong, 1993; Deereusefond *et al.*, 1993) in case $\mathcal{M}$ of all closed subsets of $\mathcal{G}$, so that the integrals are multiple Wiener integrals. Since by iterated integration formula (see theorem 5.1) any multiple Wiener integral can be represented as a sum of multiple stochastic integrals relative to the smaller class of set $\mathcal{M}$, proposition 5.1 is true (Wikipedia) in general.

Proposition 4.4

For f in $L^2(\mathcal{G})$, define

$$\hat{f}^m(g_1, g_2, \dots, g_n) = \prod_{i=1}^n f(g_i) \quad (4.9)$$

$$\text{And } W_n(f, H) = (\hat{f}^n \circ W^n)_H \quad (4.10)$$

If $\mathcal{M}$ and $\{\mathcal{F}_W(H)\}$ satisfy condition (i) -(iii) , then for $H \in \mathcal{M}$,

$$W_n(f, H) = W_n(f, J \cap H) + \sum_{m=1}^n \binom{n}{m} [\hat{f}^m(\cdot) W_{n-m}(f, I) \circ W^m]_H \quad (4.11)$$

Proof :

Observed that $\hat{f}^m$ is symmetric and $\hat{f}^n(g_1, g_2, \dots, g_n) = \hat{f}^m(g_1, g_2, \dots, g_m) \hat{f}^{n-m}(g_{m+1}, \dots, g_n)$ Thus ,equation (4.11) for $H = \mathcal{G}$ is obtained by applying the iterated integration formula to express the multiple Wiener integral $W_n(f, \mathcal{G})$ in terms of stochastic integrals relative to $\mathcal{M}$.

This work is licensed under a [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 Unported License](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/)
ISSN: 1597 – 9928 Science and Education Development Inst., Nigeria

Then (5.11) is true (Wikipedia; Deereusefond and Ustunel, 1998) in general since each side is a martingale relative to $\{\mathcal{F}_W(H): H \in \mathcal{M}\}$.

Summary and Conclusion

The major focus of this paper is to depict that under very general condition on $\mathcal{M}$, there is a canonical representation of all square- integrable Martingale with respect to $\{\mathcal{F}_W(H), H \in \mathcal{M}\}$, and there after the representation for square integrable Wiener functional which reduces to that of multiple Wiener integral for $\mathcal{M} = \{\text{all closed rectangles in } \mathbb{R}_+^n \text{ with the origin at one corner}\}$.

Formulae are given for the transformation of multiple stochastic integrals under two operations. The first is the formula for the conditional expectation of a multiple stochastic integral given $\mathcal{F}_W$ and the second operation is an iterated integral formula for expressing multiple stochastic integral defined relatively to $\mathcal{M}$ in terms of stochastic integrals in relation to another class of sets $\mathcal{M}$.

These projection formulae are very relevant more importantly the iterated integral formula; as a begin step towards a stochastic calculus in general.

References

- Chang S.J, Chung H.S and Skoug D (2009): Integral transform of functional in $\lambda^2((a, b[D, T]), J. Fourier Anal. Appl. 15.$
- Deereusefond L, Hu Y and Ustunel A.S (1993): “UnInegalite d’ interpolate Sur l’espace de Wiener functional”. *CRAS, Paris, Serie 1, Vol.317 P.1065 – 1087.*
- Deereusefond L and Ustunel A.S (1998): “ON the conditional characteristic the functions of second order wiener functional” in stochastic Analysis and Related fields P. 235 – 245 progress in probability, vol. 42. Birkhauser.
- Hajek B and Wong E (1983): Multiple Stochastic Integral, Projection & Iteration *Z Wahrscheinlichkeitstheorie, Springer Verlag 63, 349 – 368.*

Huang S.T and Cambanis S (1978): Stochastic & multiple wiener integrals for Gaussian processes. *The Annals of Probability* vol. 6, No. 4 585 - 614.

Kallenberg O (1991): On an independence criterion for multiple wiener Integral, the *Annals of Probability* 19, p 483 - 495.

Stock D.W and Varadhan S.R.S. (1979): Multidimensional Diffusion processes. Grundlehren der mathWiss 233. Springer.

Ustunel A.S (2018): Analysis on Wiener space applications arxiv: 1003. 1649v2 {math.PR}, 2018

Usunel A.S. and Zakai M. (1989): on Independence and conditioning on wiener space. *Annals of Probability* 17, p 1441 - 1453.

Usunel A.S. and Zakai M. (1992): Transformation of wiener measure under anticipative flow. Praba. Theory Relative fields 93, p91 - 136.

Wikipedia: [https://en.m.wikipedia.org/wiki/iterated integral](https://en.m.wikipedia.org/wiki/iterated_integral)